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ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS TO SUPPORT THE EXPORT OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND PROPOSALS

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Abstract:

Objective. The purpose of the study is to analyze the organizational and economic mechanisms related to the state support of industrial exports in the developed countries of the world and to identify the main trends.

Methods. The organizational and economic mechanisms of the export of industrial products used by the developed-leading exporting countries are classified using the method of comparative analysis. Analyzing the organizational and economic mechanisms of the export of industrial products, the positive aspects of using these mechanisms in the economy of our country were determined.

Results. The organizational and economic mechanisms of the export of industrial products are analyzed, and a comparative description of the mechanisms for supporting the export of industrial products in developed and leading exporting countries is based.

Conclusion. Based on the further improvement of the organizational and economic mechanisms of effective support of the export activity by the state, which is shown by the experience of developed countries, it is possible to take a place among the countries that supply competitive products in the foreign market.

Keywords: export of industrial products, organizational mechanisms, economic mechanisms, legal mechanisms, administrative mechanisms, financial mechanisms.

Introduction. Globalization processes in the world economy show that in recent years, the growth of exports of goods lags behind the growth of the world gross domestic product. Factors related to socio-economic development and competitiveness, there is a need to achieve sustainable economic development by improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of export of industrial products. According to the World Trade Organization (WTO), "world trade in goods decreased by 5.3% in 2020 and by 3.0% in 2019, significantly lower than the 2.9% increase in 2018. By 2022, it is predicted that world trade in goods may decrease to 4%². The decline in total goods trade is mainly due to the decrease in the export of industrial products. Industrial products constitute the main part of the export of goods. Therefore, in the development of world trade, the growth of the export of

industrial products has priority, which requires further improvement of organizational and economic mechanisms in the field.

Methods. Systematic analysis, synthesis, statistical grouping, expert assessments and other methods were used in the research.

Results. In our opinion, the export support under state guarantee-insurance and credit guarantee plays an important role in the export of complex technological, capital-intensive and industrial products to foreign markets. In practice, participants of various tenders and competitions with such support can get financing on more favorable terms, which in turn creates a greater chance of success.

Organizational mechanisms, which include a number of means and mechanisms for helping exporters, are

²

https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/statis_e/wts2020_e/wts2020_e.pdf

effectively used as one of the main elements of state support for exports.

Table 1.
Comparative description of export support mechanisms in developed countries³

Nº	Mechanisms	USA	Great Britain	Germany	Japan	South Korea
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	Legal	Laws and special commission control	Laws and statutory documents	Laws and federal control	Laws and special regulatory legal documents	Laws and state control
2.	Organizational	Ministry, state and non-governmental organizations	Agency, ministry	Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Economy and Energy Consortium of Private Banks AKA and KFW State Bank Group	Ministry, council and various programs	State agency
3.	Financial	Eximbank	Export Credit Guarantee Department		Japan International Cooperation State Bank	Korea Trade and Investment Development Agency
4.	Administrative	Centralized and private system	Centralized public administration	Federal, regional level	Centralized public administration	Central and regional
5.	Economical	development of consulting, financial instruments and individual marketing strategies	information-advisory, marketing, advertising services, as well as political-diplomatic support, special programs	Marketing, transportation subsidies, consulting	consulting and advertising services, lobbying	logistic support, image and brand promotion
6.	Territorial	Export assistance centers, Small Business Administration centers	Territorial divisions under the administration of the central government	Regional chambers of commerce and industry	Japan Foreign Trade Promotion Organization and its divisions	Representations of the State Agency
7.	Information and Internet resources	export.gov , business.U.S.A.gov	exportingisgreat.gov.uk	ixpos.de	jetro.go.jp/en/	http://english.kotra.or.kr

The developed countries studied on the basis of research have the following organizational means of export support:

– information and advisory support (market and marketing research, legal advice, etc.);

³ Developed by the author.

- educational and special information-educational events (seminars, webinars, etc.);
- organizing advertising, exhibitions and fairs, helping to establish business relations and cooperation with foreign partners;
- "trade-political support (improving access to foreign markets, eliminating discriminatory restrictions by ensuring effective use of WTO instruments, regional and bilateral agreements on free trade);
- political-diplomatic support (state visits, lobbying, support of investment projects and export deals, promotion of a positive business image);

- removal of excessive administrative barriers".

The mechanism of modern export support in developed countries is based on mutual cooperation of state and non-state institutions, including specialized ministries and agencies, specialized institutions and export centers, financial institutions, regional and foreign officials. In our opinion, the rich practical experience gained by these countries will serve as a program for every developing country at a time when globalization processes are rapidly deepening in the world economy (Table 1).

Table 2.

Organizational and economic mechanisms of export activity management

Management methods		Export policy implementation tools		Availability in practice
By tariffs		<i>Customs duty</i>		<i>At zero rate</i>
Quantitative restrictions		Quota, licensing		For some products and activities
Organizational and economic	Unrated	Hidden	Voluntary export restrictions	It is used by most developing countries when exporting their national products abroad under the pressure of importers to restrict exports.
		Financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies • Export credits • Anti-dumping 	Yes Yes Yes
		Creation of a system of national organizations supporting export	Promotion of national products abroad and search for new markets	"Uztreyd" JSC is a foreign trade company
Organizational and legal	Improvement of regulatory and legal documents on further development of export activities		Adapting the existing ones to the requirements of the present time, accepting the necessary ones and putting them into practice	Law, decree, decision and other legal documents
	Development of activities of legal and information-advisory organizations for exporters		Provision of legal, information-consulting and marketing services	Export support agencies

Discussions. As can be seen from the table, developed countries use various mechanisms to support the export of industrial products. Most of these mechanisms are based on state support, and in national practice, the introduction of

foreign export centers, promotion of local brands, provision of various insurance products, development of industrial export development programs at the regional level, and effective can be used. At the same time, it is considered appropriate to implement the following:

- Organization of export development agencies and export centers;
- Development of export insurance system and activities of export credit agencies;

- searching for new export markets. For example, India, as the second most populous country, has a much larger market. The next destinations are Japan and South Korea. Although South Korea is considered a strategic trading partner for us, we still have a negative balance. Japan is a giant market that imports products worth about 600 billion dollars a year, and it is necessary to master the rules of the Japanese market.

Organizational and economic mechanisms of export activity, areas of application of management methods and tools, interdependence and connection between them are presented in Table 2.

As can be seen from the table, we can see that there are a number of problems and shortcomings in the organizational and economic mechanisms of export support.

Conclusion. It is possible to take a place in the ranks of the countries that

supply competitive products in the foreign market only by using the means of effective state support for export activities, as shown by the experience of developed countries. These tools require further improvement of the organizational and economic mechanisms used by the state. Regarding the improvement of the organizational and economic mechanisms of export activity, the following can be suggested:

- help exporters obtain international certificates and licenses that fully meet the requirements of world standards, including Global GAP, ISO and other documents;
- finding foreign partners for entrepreneurs and helping to sign export contracts by studying the demand of foreign countries for products and services;
- regular involvement of enterprises in export activities in the region and organization of meetings dedicated to the discussion of emerging problematic issues;
- to study sales channels of industrial products in the region;
- to propose the direction of improvement of the product and price policy in the industrial sector and the systems of promotion of product sales;
- it is necessary to carry out important studies that ensure the increase in the efficiency of product export in industrial enterprises.

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